

Historical Trajectories of Ayurveda and Health Tourism: A Descriptive Approach

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Abstract

Ayurveda and other alternative medicines are gaining popularity in many European countries. People are increasingly depends on holistic approaches to health and wellness, especially for chronic conditions like arthritis, digestive disorders, stress-related ailments, and many life style diseases. Ayurveda is a holistic system of medicine with preventive health care and personalised medicines. In many European countries such as Germany, UK and Italy students can combine their medicine studies with Ayurveda in their post graduate level. This research paper is conceived with two objectives: to throw some initial light about the long historical journey of Ayurveda in a course of over three millennia and to analyse with particular clarity its modern paradigms which set the context for the origin of health tourism.

Introduction

The structural transformation of Ayurveda from being a system of medicine to an industry which engages in the production for the market is a classic example to study how a traditional knowledge system undergoes modernization and commercialisation. Ayurveda has become a transnational and multicultural phenomenon ever since its interface with modernity. New paradigms develop within the system and new theories and practices get added alongside the established ones. Health tourism is a recent development in this indigenous medical system. This

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novel phenomenon could be juxtaposed along with other major trends such as Ayurvedic pharmaceutical research, academic textual research, drug development and industrial production. The religious, political and cultural climates set by globalisation made it possible for Ayurveda to have a Diaspora in the world beyond its original homeland in South Asia.

What motivates this constant evolution within a system of general medicine with preventative and prescriptive functions deserves our particular attention. Steven Shapin hints a clue in his proposition that individuals and groups produce scientific knowledge not in isolation but against the background of their culture's inherited knowledge and their collectively situated purposes as well as through the information they receive from natural reality (Steven Shapin, 1982). Knowledge is not timeless but it is moulded heavily by emergent conditions and social needs. This explains the development of a wide variety of oral and textual traditions in India over the course of millennia. Time and again, exogenous encounters as well as the contacts with indigenous roots re-shaped our knowledge system. Given the cultural plurality, multiple scientific traditions developed in India in the pre-colonial times.

The trajectories followed by Ayurveda in different regions of the Indian subcontinent doesn't follow uniformity but were distinct. However in the face of modernity, the traditional medical system across the country negotiated with western medicine and underwent institutionalization in manufacturing and professionalization in training. Consequently, the local knowledge was incorporated into global discourse.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

1. To search about the long historical journey of Ayurveda in a course of over three millennia
2. To analyse with particular clarity its modern paradigms that set the context for the origin of health tourism.

Antecedents in the Vedic Age C. 1500 BC – 500 BC

Vedic Age which commenced in the mid-second millennium BC represents the earliest historical period in India. Traditional literatures take it for granted that the roots of Ayurveda lie

in the Vedas. Origin-myths of Ayurveda maintain that a series of meetings were held in the Himalayas for the derivation of Ayurvedic knowledge. Accordingly the divinity of Indra revealed texts to Charaka and Sushruta through Agnivesha and Dhanvantari respectively. Although we could not set the point of departure for historical investigations in these myths, these primitive textual ties had utility in as much as they inspired later medical authors to take forward their pursuit of advancing knowledge.

The nomenclature of Ayurveda suggests it to be the knowledge (*veda*) of longevity (*ayus*). It could be more meaningfully paraphrased as the science of life or as an empirical system of healing. The immediate question that follows this nomenclatural analysis is whether Vedic Age truly features the origins of Ayurveda. The Vedic literary corpus including *samhitas*, *sutras*, *upanishads*, *aranyakas* and *brahmanas* forms the earliest literature of India. However they were meant to be the liturgy for the ritual practices for the ancient Indo-Aryans who held hegemony over the Vedic epoch. These texts were not intended as narratives about medicine but about religion. But certain parts of these literary texts, particularly the Atharva-veda throw some light on the earliest history of medicine in Indian subcontinent. In the pages of this text we come across certain prayers, spells and charms which were purposed to bring good health and to stave off malevolent deities which caused diseases.

In a final analysis taking into consideration the whole Vedic literature, it becomes more clear that the medical ideas and practices suggested in them doesn't qualify as obvious precursor to the Ayurvedic system in its classical vigour. Differences are overwhelming and similarities are least in a comparative study of both literatures. To put an example, we could not see even a clear reference to the most fundamental Ayurvedic principle of humours (*dosas*) in Vedic literature. It could then be logically inferred that the classical system of Ayurveda originated later. Where the medical histories do not suggest any evidences for Vedic origin of Ayurveda, it may be hypothesized that the authors of Ayurvedic literature in later periods might have claimed Ayurvedic derivation from the Vedas in order for religious sanction and social acceptance. What emerge out of this discussion is that the medical growth in Vedic period which was exclusively

brahmanical was rigid, underdeveloped and intertwined with religion and magical practices (tantra and mantra) (P.Bala 1991).

Preliminary Developments C. 500 BC – 300 BC

At about the close of Vedic period c. 500 BC, northern India witnessed the beginnings of a new social formation featured by second urbanization and the advent and spread of Buddhism. Brahmanism continued to flourish but ascetic lifestyle became a popular trend. Ayurveda probably emerged as a recognizable system in this new context. Codification of Ayurvedic knowledge in a series of treatises began from this period onwards. An inherent advantage of this era was the development of monasteries by Buddhist missionaries (D.P.Chattopadhyay 1983). The strict and enlightened environment of such abbeys helped to evolve Ayurveda as a more rational therapeutics, though not complete. It is certain that the post-Vedic age marked a partial move away from the earlier loops in which knowledge was inextricably tied up with religious beliefs and ritualistic practices.

It is fitting here to take a brief look at the basic tenets of Ayurveda as it was in the period under our consideration. Given the existence of a web of several different layers of histories and traditions, it is quite hard to pick one simple set of ideas and postulate them as the fundamental principles of Ayurveda. However the early Buddhist texts put forward first explicit statements that the diseases arise from an imbalance of humoral substances in the body. The idea of humours was to become a fundamental principle in Indian medical theory for several centuries. This formulation was systematically put forward for the first time in Post-Vedic period. According to the doctrine of three humours (*Tridosavidya*), there are three semi-fluid substances present in human body to regulate its state of affairs. The humours are wind (*vata*), cholera (*pitta*) and phlegm (*kapha*). Interestingly, this doctrine is very much analogous to the ancient Greek humoral system derived by Hippocrates. The humours interact with seven basic constituents of the body: chyl, blood, flesh, fat, bone, marrow, and semen. They also interact with the body's waste products. The Ayurvedic medication in its preliminary phase was centred on animals and vegetables. A wide variety of therapies such as surgery, diet, massage, bloodletting, enemas, and ointments were also in practice in this initial period of Ayurvedic development.

The Classical Age of Ayurveda C. 300 BC - AD 600

After its initial growth in Post-Vedic period featured by Buddhist asceticism, Ayurveda underwent further development and emerged into its classical period by around third century BC. Ayurveda's classical age was also the period in which Mahabharata was narrated in a course of few centuries. The two most important texts composed in this period could be taken as the starting point in classical Ayurvedic literature: the compendia of Charaka (*CharakaSamhita*) and Sushruta (*SushrutaSamhita*). Both are significant for the vast amount of information they suggest about different aspects of medical science: diagnosis, pharmacopoeia and clinical practice (Wujastyk 1998). They are absolutely centrepieces to Ayurveda.

These two texts along with Ashtanga-hridayaSamhita (Heart of the eight limbs of medicine) composed by Vagbhata in early seventh century are considered as the Brihat-Trayi (Great Three) among the Ayurvedic texts. Alongside the grouping of the Great Three, there is a Lesser Threesome too in Ayurvedic literature. They are the texts composed by Madhava in seventh century, Sarngadhara in fourteenth and Bhavamisra in seventeenth centuries.

Fully fledged classical system of Ayurveda emerges in the compendia of Charaka and Sushruta which can be called as the earliest purely medical literature in India. Both these ancient physicians have devoted several important chapters in both their classical texts to analyse fever (jvara). Many herbal recipes are put forward in both texts. A brief glance at the schematisation of these two texts may be fitting here.

Charaka's Compendium

CharakaSamhita is the text with which classical medicine in India really begins. Charaka is dated at around third and second centuries B.C. A very significant discussion undertaken by him is about the growth of the embryo and its result in childbirth. It throws clear light of real medical practices in 120 chapters which can be grouped into eight parts.

1. *Cikitsa*: on therapy
2. *Indriya*: on diagnosis and prognosis
3. *Kalpa*: on pharmacy

4. *Nidana*: on the causes of eight main diseases
5. *Sarira*: on philosophy, anatomy and embryology
6. *Siddhi*: on further general therapy
7. *Sutra*: on pharmacology, food, diet, some diseases and treatments, physicians and quacks, and varied topics in philosophy
8. *Vimana*: on tastes, nourishment, general pathology and medical studies

CharakaSamhita deals with the elaborated and detailed descriptions on the anatomy of the human body, body functions and dysfunctions based on the equilibrium of the liquid parts of the body such as *vata*, *pitta* and *kapha*, and the etiology of the diseases on basis of Tridosha theory. There are also in it chapters on fetal generation and development, etiology, classification, pathology, diagnosis, prognosis, treatment of various diseases including those of the eyes, the female genital organs, normal and abnormal deliveries, diseases of children and the science of rejuvenation of the body. Charaka's "*Materia-Medica*" gave detailed description on drugs based on vegetable, animal and earthy products and classified them into 50 groups on the basis of their reaction on the body. Some noteworthy commentaries on CharakaSamhita are *Ayurveda-dipika* by Chakrapanidatta, *Nirantar-pad-vyakhya* by Jajjata, *Charaka-tattva-pradipika* by Shiva Das and *Jalpa-kalpa-taruby* Ganga Dhar. It was translated in to Arabic in eighth century and its English translation by A.C. Kaviratna came in to light in 1897.

Sushruta's Compendium

SushrutaSamhita in the form which we have received as the oldest surviving manuscript is not a work of single person. It is text behind which several hands worked. Several historical layers, could, therefore be traced in this text. The narration of the text started sometime in the closing centuries B.C. and reached in its final form by A.D. 500. This compendium is particularly significant for its description of ophthalmic surgery. The text is put in five sections.

1. *Cikitsa*: on therapy
2. *Kalpa*: on poisons
3. *Nidhana*: on symptoms, embryology and anatomy

4. *Sutra*: on some general questions about the origin and division of medicine, medical training, diet, surgery and treatment of wounds
5. *Uttara*: on ophthalmology, the care of children, dentistry and diseases ascribed to demonic attacks

SushrutaSamhita was originally known as *Salya-tantra*. It was revised and supplemented by another Sushruta (Sushruta the younger) through whom the knowledge on surgery came to being in ancient India. SusrutaofSalya-tantra was a reputed teacher and an admirable author. The general technique of surgery was greatly improved by his contributions. Students of Susruta practiced surgical treatments on dummies and on dead bodies. His technique of dissection is unique, practical and revealing of the structure of the body. His operations for making a new nose or ear-lobe, lithotomy, taking out the dead foetus and abdominal operations are classical marvels. Before Susruta the surgical knowledge of India was at par with that of Egypt, Mesopotamia and Greece and with his contributions it went far ahead of those of its counterparts. Major commentaries on *SusrutaSamhita* are *Bhanumati* by Chakrapanidatta written in 11th century A.D. and *NibandhaSamgraha* by Dalhana written in 12th century A.D.

Maturation of the System C. AD 600 – AD 900

The Classical Ayurveda represented by CharakaSamhita and SushrutaSamhita underwent a further maturity in the succeeding centuries leading up to medievalism. It is already said that Vagbhata's Ashtanga-hridaya composed in seventh century is grouped in the Great Three alongside Charaka and Sushruta. Many among the important Ayurvedic texts that have survived to this date were written in this period.

A brief reflection on the general perspective that runs through these texts will throw light into the development of Ayurveda. The central process in body was conceived as digestion. Fire (*agni*) is depicted in the texts as the digestive force. *Ojas* (energy) was conceptualised as the ultimate motive force of the body and the source of its strength. Hence diet is given particular attention in all these texts. Diseases arise when parts of the complex bodily process go wrong. As for medication, the practice of oiling and sweating the patients became a norm before many

therapies. Towards the close of this period, metallic compounds were being increasingly used in medicine. Introduction of opium in treatment was a later addition which began from the advent of Islam in India.

Vagbhata's Ashtanga-Hridaya

Ashtanga-hridaya (Heart of the Medicine) by Vagbhata composed in seventh century is accounted as the greatest synthesis of Indian medicine ever produced. It eclipsed even the texts by Charaka and Sushruta in multiple ways. Vagbhata systematically codified all the disordered and conflicting medical data. This scholar from Sind (modern Karachi in Pakistan) learnt Charaka and Sushruta and presented a new text as a well-organized and thematically structured composition. Thus many parts of this text were either extracted from or modelled on texts written in earlier times. It gives full expression to the richness and detail of the ancient Indian medical tradition. Vagbhata puts forward hundreds of recipes, details of behaviour and procedure, options, variations and permutations in Ashtanga-hridaya.

The text was translated in the countries in India's neighbourhood soon after its composition. It influenced the medical traditions of entire Asia. The impact of this text can be comprehended from the fact that the students throughout the medieval period in India memorized it as the core of their medical education. In the conservative circles of Ashtavaidya families of Kerala, certain scholars learn this text by heart even today! *AshtangaHridayaSamhita* is composed in 120 chapters. It gives a concise description of Ayurvedic medicine with specific emphasis on surgery. The author quotes Charaka, Susruta, Bhela, Kasyapa, Dhanvantari and other earlier authors and their works. Arudatta's *Sarvangasundari* (1220 A.D) and Hemadri's *Ayurveda Rasayana* written sometime between A.D. 1271-1309 are the two most important commentaries of this text.

Vagbhata's AshtangaSamgraha

A second major work ascribed to Vagbhata is AshtangaSamgraha. It can be translated as the Tome on Medicine. Certain scholars opine that this text was not authored by Vagbhata given its different style. Unlike the other text, AshtangaSamgraha is narrated as a prose in a quit

different style. It is considerably longer too. But Wujastyk holds that because there is a great deal in common for both the texts, they could have come from single author.

AshtangaSamgraha is written in 150 chapters grouped into five sections. The first section is about the practice of medicine. It describes the initiation of the students, longevity and the methods of attaining it, daily and seasonal observances, origin of diseases, properties of different food articles such as rice, meat, herbs, fruits, characteristics of poisoned food, treatment after having taken poisoned food, precautions to be observed by the kings, personal hygiene, drugs and their sub divisions; collection, composition, taste, strength, qualities, and actions of medicinal substances; emetic and astringent drugs; three humours *vata*, *pitta*, and *kapha* and their derangement; various diseases; examination of the patient, principles of treatment; snuffs, fumigants, gargles, treatment of eye diseases with soothing applications and eye drops; extraction of foreign bodies.

The second section focuses on human anatomy. It describes the changes in the structure of the foetus during pregnancy, management of difficult labour and diseases of pregnancy, anatomy of the human body, vascular system, vital parts of the body, nature of man, different types of men and their characteristics, abnormal characters, prognosis based on shadows and messengers. The third section describes the causes and pathology of various conditions such as fever, haemorrhage, asthma, phthisis, delirium tremens, piles, diarrhoea, and retention of urine, diabetes, deep-seated abscesses, abdominal diseases, anaemia, leprosy, skin diseases, and diseases of the nervous system. The fourth section is on purgation and vomiting.

The fifth section describes about the management of children, diseases of children, demonical seizures in children, and their treatment, diseases caused by super human influences and their treatment; treatment of insanity, epilepsy, various diseases of the eyes including blindness and inflammations, diseases of the ear, nose, mouth, head, ulcers, wounds, fractures, fistulas, glandular enlargements, minor diseases, diseases of the organs of generation, treatment of poisoning, snake, insect, spider, and mouse bites, antidotes, rejuvenation and the use of aphrodisiacs. Commentaries on *AshtangaSamgraha* were written by Arunadatta about 1220 A.D. and by Hemadri a few decades later.

Kasyapa's Compendium

KasyapaSamhita is an ancient Ayurvedic text by sage MarichaKasyapa dealt. Its primary focus is on the curatives for the diseases of children. It gives details about teething in children, names of the teeth and the time they appear and the accompanying symptoms. The text also refers to rickets and on the use of garlic. The original form of *KasyapaSamhita* is lost and we have its redaction by Vatsya of Gupta period.

Other important texts

A brief list of other important texts which emerged in the period under consideration and in later medieval period follows for an immediate reference.

1. *BhelaSamhita* by Bhela
2. *ChikitsaKalika* by Tishtacharya
3. *Madhavanidana* by Madhavakara
4. *Rasaratnakara* by Nagarjuna
5. *Gunasamgraha* by Sothal
6. *Sarangadhara-padhati* by Sarangadhara
7. *Bhavaprakasha* and *Gunaratnamala* by Bhavamisra
8. *Siva TattvaRatnakara* by KeladiBasava Raja

TheAyurvedic Medievalism c. AD 900 – AD 1700

Medieval period witnessed an important paradigm shift in Ayurvedic progression in the sub-continent. Efforts at systematising traditional medical knowledge accelerated in several parts of northern India. New texts were continually being composed, new paradigms were explored and influences from many other areas of Indian discourse were introduced into the medical system after AD 900. However, a major share of Ayurvedic texts of medievalism remains unknown and unstudied by a larger public.

A major question which concerns this period is whether Ayurveda declined in the course of Islamic rule in India. Although scholars are divided over this question, Jan Meulenbeld (2002) counters these criticisms upon his historical investigations. He suggests that there emerged a dynamic and syncretise Indo-Muslim culture in the course of medievalism. This syncretism functioned as a mutual enrichment such that there came into being a creative synthesis between Hindu Ayurveda and Islamic Unani systems. Furthermore, evidences suggest that the Hindu seats of learning in Benares and Nadia in Bengal continued to flourish side by side Mughal rule in India. Medievalism was an age of fruitful intermingling of scientific traditions in India. Islamic culture interacted with the Indian environment and the region's rich *material medica*.

Exchange of biological information accelerated particularly among Asia and Europe in the later medieval period (Richard Grove 1998). Scientific and medical exchanges were realised through the agency and impetus of trade, warfare, migration of scholars, merchants, physicians and craftsmen in Islamic world and Europe. Consequently, much of the Ayurvedic schematization as represented in ancient classical texts were replaced by newer encounters, internal developments, refinements in medical knowledge, a changing ecology and due to the influence of ever changing indigenous religious and cultural forms. A case study of such medieval transformations undergone by Ayurveda can be had from the development of Ashtavaidya in Kerala.

Ashtavaidya Tradition in Medieval Kerala

Ayurvedic practitioners in medieval Kerala were not exclusively Brahmans. Several EzhavaVaidyas belonging to Ashtavaidya flourished in the state in the entire course of medievalism. Alongside the classical Ayurveda traditions, several indigenous folk medicinal practices had evolved in Kerala in its unique geography. Thus, according to P.R.Varier, there were many families in Kerala who were specialists in one or more therapies such as *uzhichil* (massage), *marmacikilsa* (treatment for diseases of certain vital parts of the body), *balacikilsa* (pediatrics), *netracikilsa* (ophthalmology), *visacikilsa* (toxicology) and *bhutapasmarapratividhi* (psychiatric treatment).

Ayurveda made a flourishing growth in the state since sixteenth century. Brahmans and Ezhavas made efforts to study Vagbhata's texts *Ashtanga-hridaya* and *AshtangaSamgraha*. They practiced Ayurveda as their vocation and with great passion. They were called Ashtavaidyas, given their specialization in eight important branches of Ayurveda. Ashtavaidyafamilies had played a great role for securing a unique position for Kerala in Ayurvedic practice. The theoretical and practical knowledge of Ashtavaidyas contributed much to the retention and dissemination of ancient knowledge.

Ashtavaidya tradition evolved in a process of blending Ayurveda of *Ashtangahridayam* with the local knowledge and practices of folk healers. Ashtavaidyas developed their own therapeutics in the course of time. Much of the medicinal secrets were considered to be ancestral secrets. However disciples from outside traditional Ashtavaidya families had also mastered this knowledge system in various parts of Kerala. Sanskrit commentaries of Ashtavaidyas like *Hridayabothika* and *Vakyapradipika* had enriched the literature of Ayurveda. *AlatturManipravalam*, *Cikilsamanjari*, *Sahasrayogam* and *Sindhuramanjari* were the major compendia in Malayalam by Ashtavaidyas.

The Colonial Encounters of Ayurveda C. AD 1700 - AD 1850

The next major trajectorial shift for Ayurveda was in its encounter with the West against the background of colonialism. The history of modern and global Ayurveda begins with the encounter between Indian and European practitioners of medicine through the spice trade (Patterson 1987). When the colonialists from Europe made their way into the Indian sub-continent, they found that India's traditional medical system has had different developments in different regions of the country.

Orientalists among the colonialists were interested in probing into Indian culture and traditions. Some of the 18th century European orientalist even put that the ancient Indian civilization was equal to and in some respects even excellent than classical Greece and Rome. They perceived the remarkable advancements made by Hindu medical science before the dawn of the Christian era. They ascribed as the reasons for the Ayurveda's decline in the rigidity of

caste system, Islamic rule in India which believed that the old Indian civilization is destructive and the anarchy in the country after the break-up of Mughal Empire into regional warring factions.

Some of them who were interested in Indology were set to discover roots of Indian medicine. They printed and translated medical texts and wrote summaries of their contents. Such scholarships were of less practical use but important contribution to formalize Ayurvedic education and research in subsequent periods. Europeans made efforts to systematise India's traditional medical knowledge. HortusIndicusMalabaricus written under the stewardship of Dutch colonists with the help of EzhavaVaidya Itty Achutan and others is a classic example of European interest to codify botanical knowledge from local society(M.SHarilal 2008). British explorations in Indian tropics reached up to greater heights later. Orientalist scholarship continued even after decolonization but in a new form in 1960s through the initiatives of such scholars as Charles Leslie who created new public perceptions of Ayurveda through medical anthropology.

Another important issue to perceive in the analysis of colonial encounters of Ayurveda is the patterns of its interactions with the Western medicine. In this direction, George Basalla theorized a diffusionist model in 1967. Accordingly, the modern science diffused from its original home in Western Europe to the rest of the world (George Basalla, 1967) British believed in their superiority and responsibility over lands which they identified as superstitious and backward. They saw medicine as an attribute of their civilizing mission. In the first phase of this process, Europeans established contact with new lands in Asia and Africa through trade and colonisation. This facilitated Europeans to conduct systematic exploitation of ecology in the colonies which they did through construction of maps, surveys, botany, zoology and geography. Second phase witnessed the establishment of local scientific communities in the colonies. In the third phase, natives in the colonies responded by the creation of national science. Thus the colonies achieved maturation into independent scientific traditions. Basalla's model is challenged now by many others. Certain elements in this model are right but this extremely Eurocentric version claimed that the modern science originated exclusively in the West. Hence

Bassala's arguments suffer from a defect that it totally underestimates the complex experience of India and other such countries into oversimplified typologies.

The British health and education policy in India in the opening decades of 19th century was to support new medical knowledge and methodologies which were then emerging in Europe. This they did by extending patronage to new medical colleges and hospitals which produced a number of practitioners with a medical reputation superior to that of traditional practitioners. Such a context became a real challenge for the practitioners of Ayurveda. Now they had to meet competition from the part of allopathy. In order to prove the efficacy and utility of Ayurveda, they felt need to evolve theoretical foundations of their medical system and to establish their professional identity. The period marked the beginnings of modern Ayurveda when its practitioners organized into uniform body. If traditionally knowledge dissemination in Ayurveda was done through pupillage system, now it expanded towards a college system. In their search for a uniform identity, they learned to overcome sectarian and regional differences as well. All these survival strategies adopted by Ayurvedic practitioners in the sidelines of colonialism set the context for its modernization.

Modernization of Ayurveda c. AD 1850 - AD 1950

The elites among the Ayurvedic practitioners in India stand for the necessity to modernize the system in order to complement western medicine which was set to establish its scientific hegemony and unassailable superiority in India. They positively comprehended about scientific and industrial progress in the West and began to introspect on indigenous medical system, religions and society in the light of scientific reason (GyanPrakash, 1996). By late nineteenth century, Indians were convinced that the authority of western science couldn't be ignored. The only alternative before the natives was to engage in revitalisation through reforms. Lucien Pye formulates that modernization of a system essentially means its openness to advanced technology, spirit of science, a rational view of life and a secular approach to social relations. In late nineteenth and early twentieth centuries, Indian scientists and intellectuals tried to construct their own brand of Indian modernity, particularly through the selective incorporation or re-invention of Hindu ideas and traditions. State regulation and

patronage, efforts for mass manufacturing, systematic education, research and standardization techniques, introduction of modern mould of production, low cost and easy accessibility particularly helped in the hastening of Ayurveda.

Towards Institutionalization

The Ayurvedic revival assumed several forms. The most fundamental among them was the institutionalization and modernization of the system. In order to stand the test of competition from allopathy, Ayurveda had to respond on different fronts. The location and translation of Ayurvedic texts from Sanskrit into English was one of the first methods towards institutionalization. In this process, major Ayurvedic works were made accessible to a wide audience. Next, the nationalists tried to establish strong local roots for indigenous medicine by setting up Ayurvedic dispensaries in several cities and towns across the country. Dispensaries were then one of the most distinctive and effective institutional forms of Western medicine. The emulation of this method worked positively for Ayurvedic revival. Indigenous medicine was popularised through the printing press either as newspaper articles or as advertisements. Inability of western medical practitioners to deal promptly with cholera, malaria, plague, influenza and syphilis made it possible for Ayurveda, Unani and Homeopathy to propose remedies. A landmark attempt in professionalization of Ayurveda was the initiation of All India Ayurveda Mahasammelan (Ayurvedic Congress) in 1907. Indigenous medical practitioners put several attempts to supplant superstitious folk practices as well. The indigenous system received further impetus when for some time, Ayurvedic courses were taught along with allopathic training in Medical colleges run by the British. Consequently, Ayurveda was transformed radically with the advent of production, marketing, research. In course of time, indigenous therapeutics evolved as a cultural alternative to allopathy.

Modernization of Ayurveda in Kerala

The Transformation of Ayurveda along modern lines in Kerala was realized through two-prong efforts. Attempts for institutionalisation were patronaged by the princely state in Travancore while the modernization of the system was realized through the individual initiative of P.S. Varier in Malabar.

The government in Travancore perceived that oral traditional and the code of secrecy were real barriers for non-experts to enter into the field of Ayurveda. In order to advance the theoretical setting of the medical system, government decided to start Ayurveda College which would effectively replace gurukula system of knowledge dissemination. First such Ayurvedic College was established in Thiruvananthapuram in 1886. The Travancore model was later emulated elsewhere in the country. Punjab had its first Ayurvedic College in 1898 and Uttar Pradesh in 1899. The government of Travancore made efforts to run a number of Taluqvaidyasalas in the state with grants-in-aid provided by the state. Thiruvananthapuram Ayurveda Patasala was also a step for institutionalising the system.

Modernization of Ayurveda in Malabar was initiated by P.S. Varier. His career and ideas are crucial to understand Ayurvedic movement in Kerala. Varier was born in 1869. As a young man, he learned initial lessons of Ayurveda from a prominent Vaidyan for four years. He managed to learn English and western allopathy from an allopathic surgeon at Government Hospital in Manjeri, He was determined to raise Ayurveda from disrepute. With this objective in mind, he established practice at Kottackal in Malabar. Here he demonstrated the valued qualities and efficacy of the Ayurvedic medicines. He integrated Ayurvedic and Allopathic components and established KottackalAryaVaidyasala(Panikkar1995). In 1902 he launched AryaVaidyaSamajam and drew up his own manifesto for an Ayurvedic revival. Several Ayurvedic conferences were held by this platform. In the same year he initiated the launch of a journal titled AryaVaidyan. He wanted to popularize Ayurveda and move it out of old ruts. He was willing in this process to adopt modern techniques without detriment to inherent qualities of indigenous medicine. He held that the reason for people to lose confidence in the Ayurvedic system as a whole was because patients used to receive ineffective medicines. Therefore, he continually persuaded Vaidyans not to rely on illiterate apothecaries to prepare their drugs. He asked them to learn to prepare drugs themselves and to maintain the standards of drugs they used. Wherever useful and necessary, modern ways of standardisation should be initiated in this process. KottackalAyurvedicPatasala was conceived as a solution to this lacuna in production and training. His ideas were put into effect by setting up an Ayurvedic

pharmaceutical company, the monthly sale of which by his death in 1944 was approximately Rs. 30000(Kizhdath Vasudevan Nair 1954).

Ayurvedic movement strengthened in such local beginnings and grass-root interactions with western medicine. While the colonial state supported allopathy, maharajas, landed magnates and professional middle classes supported the cause of Ayurvedic revivalism. Reformed Ayurveda squeezed out unscientific practitioners. Allopathy continued to be politically dominant but Ayurveda successfully made its quest for cultural hegemony in 19th and 20th centuries (Panikkar 1992).

Changes in Production Relations

M.S. Harilal distinguishes between three stages in the production of Ayurvedic medicine. He conceived familial mode of production as the first stage in this evolution. In this preliminary context, productive activity was not governed primarily by the objective of maximising profit and achieving a monetary surplus but geared towards subsistence needs of the family and the need to maintain self-sufficiency. Medicine was a no-price good in this phase. The large numbers of small dispensaries established and run by the Ashtavaidyas across south India exemplify this phase. Treatment was provided free of cost in such dispensaries. Practitioners believed that receiving remuneration for Ayurvedic treatment would nullify the effect of the medicine (Vinayachandran 2001). Physician's family often served as the unit of production. Clearly, Ayurvedic medicine was not a commodity and no remunerations were drawn on medicine. In the context of Kerala, this phase is considered as the period before 1830s.

Outbreak of cholera and smallpox created a need for more organized production of Ayurvedic medicine. Such situations compelled the transformation of Ayurvedic production into next stage. The second phase in production relations represents petty production. The period between 1830s and 1880s is understood as the proto-industrial system of Ayurveda. The period from 1880s onwards marks the third stage. The fundamental feature of this period is the entry of capital which was realized in late 19th and early 20th centuries. The initiators of this phase such as P.S. Varier and Ajmal Khan had employed various strategies for shaping the

market for Ayurveda. The products were networked through regional outlets and distributed through native governmental departments. Stepping into market during epidemic with new commodities was also a technique which worked. For instance, Varier marketed Vishchikari pills based on his own research at the time of cholera's outbreak. What followed in this third phase were modernization and mechanization. Ayurveda's nature shifted from being a service sector to a pharmaceutical sector. Subsequently this unorganized sector gradually evolved as a sector which was largely dependent on the large scale manufacturers. In 1920s there were at least ten Ayurvedic manufacturing firms engaged in large scale production and marketing.

Ayurvedic Revival and Nationalist Ideology

In the course of Ayurvedic revivalism, an interesting methodology adopted by certain Hindu writers was to view western science and technology as antithetical or inferior to Eastern spirituality. They formulated that Western materialism was ultimately inferior to the spiritual and intellectual legacy of the Indian religious and philosophical traditions. Science in the West merely fed material wants and desires. Ancient India showed how man could be the master, not the slave of science. Those revivalists postulated the Eastern cultivation of the science of the spirit stands over the lower science of material objects which flourished in the West.

Another group of revivalists such as Keshab Chandra Sen, Dayananda Saraswati and Vivekananda attempted to appropriate the West to the East and thus to arrive at harmony between both systems. Among them, Brajendranath Seal, a Professor of Philosophy at Calcutta University wrote in detail about the mechanical, physical and chemical theories of the ancient Hindus. He drew heavily on Ayurvedic texts to retrieve the methodological and technical achievements of ancient India. He acknowledged that in some fields, early Hindus' scientific understanding was defective but on the whole it was no less than Greeks. The whole movement of Hindu science was genuinely and positively scientific; though arrested at an early stage of its development (Seal 1915). Seal held that Bhaskaracharya and Vachaspati anticipated by centuries the work of Newton and Descartes. He further held that what rishis had was 'felicitous intuition earned by intense meditation and guided by intelligent observation'

J.C. Bose saw no contradiction between Hindu philosophy and the methodological exactitude required in modern scientific research. He asserted to a London audience the validity of the message “proclaimed by my ancestors on the banks of the Ganges thirty centuries ago.” He postulated that India was a country where science and religion could engage without any conflict because; here knowledge is regarded as a religion itself (Bose 1920). He always held up Indians’ keen imagination, intuition and understanding of the interconnectedness of all life forms. In many respects Indian approaches better suited to sensitive research than were those by Western scientists, whose approach was aggressive and crudely materialistic, and whose tendency constantly to subdivide scientific fields precluded them from seeing the underlying unity.

There were attempts for reformed Hindu medicine and a pursuit of ‘pure Ayurveda.’ In 1895 BhagvatSinhji (Maharaja of Gondal) wrote *Aryan Medical Science* and suggested that the Aryans were the most enlightened race in the dawn of history. He held that the Hindu medicine reached the acme of its glory in the time of the Ramayana and Mahabharata. However Sinhji didn’t expect revived Ayurveda entirely to supplant the Western system. KavirajGananathSen’s texts argued that the spirit of Ayurveda was the spirit of progress (Sen 1916). T.R. Ethirajulu Naidu (1918) maintained that Ayurvedic drugs being the product of a tropical country better suits for use by Indians than drugs developed in the cold climate and alien cultural conditions of temperate Europe. The Revival of Indigenous Medicine made its way possible within the discourse of intense nationalist ideology.

Ayurvedic Texts in Modernity

In the previous century, a number of texts emerged in Ayurvedic tradition by blending eastern and western principles of medicine. Selections of such texts which qualify to be an introductory encyclopaedic reference are listed below.

1. *Anugrahamimamsa* by VadakkeppattuNarayayanan Nair
2. *Arogyacintamani, Garbharaksakramam* and *VaidyaJivanam* by MahakaviVallathol
3. *Arogyakalpadrumam* by Kaikulannara Rama Varier

4. *AryaVaidyaCharitambyP.V.Krishnavarya*
5. *AshtangaSariram and Brhacchariram by VaidyaratnamP.SVariyar*
6. *Ayurveda Clinical Research by PanditaRajanTrikkovilAcutaVariar*
7. *Ayurveda Parichaya by VaidyabhushanK.RagavanTirumulpadu*
8. *AyurvedatinteAdistanaTatwangalby Pandit C. Ramakrishnan Nair*
9. *PratyaksaSarira* and *Siddhantanidana* by
MahamahopadhyayaKavirajGananathSenSaraswati
10. *Sariram* by Dr.L.ARavivarma

Responses of Colonial Government to the Revival of Ayurveda

While several attempts for Ayurvedic revival were put in by nationalists, the attitude of the colonial state and its senior medical officers towards indigenous medicine was that of hostility. For instance the Provincial Medical Registration Act in Bombay in 1912 recognized practitioners of western medicine but excluded all others. Members of the legislatures took up the cause of indigenous medicine as a result of which governmental committees were constituted to investigate on the scientific integrity of Ayurvedic medicines in Bombay and Madras.

Unlike most other officers, Sir Pardy Lukis, Director General of the IMS in 1916 commended positively for Ayurveda. “Since ninety percentage of the population lived in the countryside and had little access to Western medicine, it makes sense to support indigenous medicine to meet the basic health needs of the people”, said him. However his views were not widely shared in IMS and therefore had little practical results.

The resolutions of Congress in 1918 and 1920 called for the establishment of schools, colleges and hospitals for instruction and treatment in accordance with the indigenous systems (Jeffrey 1988).The colonial government took those resolutions seriously and the Home Department set up an Indigenous Drugs Committee to investigate the use of indigenous medicine. But it yielded few practical results because of the antagonism from European

physicians, many of whom did not feel justified in experimenting with unknown and doubtful drugs when they already had others (Report of proceedings of the Central Indigenous Drugs Committee of India 1899). However, by the 1920s and 1930s science in India had attained a new maturity and authority (Arnold 2004).

Globalisation of Ayurveda Since 1950s

In the eve of independence in 1947, a committee was set up to suggest ways of enhancing the usefulness of indigenous medicines to the public. The tone of the report was sympathetic positively towards Ayurveda but overall message confirmed the superiority of allopathic medicine (Report of the Committee of Indigenous Medicine 1948). After independence, it became increasingly clear that Ayurveda could not flourish in future exclusively through its classical poly-herbal formulations (Khare et.al., (2012). The Government set up certain important formal structures in order to flourish Ayurveda through novelties in the system. The Bhore (1946) and Mudaliar (1962) reports were the chief influences in forming the administrative and organizational establishment of national health care in India after independence (Wujastyk 1987). The principal supports in both the reports were given to Modern Establishment Medicine and secondary support for indigenous health systems in an integrated form. Accordingly, following structures were erected by the government in due course of time.

1. Central Institute of Research in Indigenous Systems of Medicine, 1956
2. Central Council for Ayurvedic Research, 1959
3. Central Council of Indian Medicine, 1971
4. Central Council for Research in Ayurveda and Siddha, 1978
5. Department of Indian Systems of Medicine, 1995 (with a permanent secretary within the Indian Ministry of Health and Family Welfare)

Meanwhile Ayurveda was set to undergo its course of globalization. Ayurvedic pharmacopoeia emerged as a scientific discipline stripped of religious and spiritual

connotations in Ayurveda. New Age Ayurveda emerged by re-interpreting the philosophical and spiritual aspects of Ayurveda(Wujastyk et.al.2008). New Age Ayurveda has given rise to a new commercialised form of Ayurveda, emphasizing wellness and beauty as fundamental components of good health. Its commercial offerings include a range of cosmetic and massage treatments provided in beauty salons and spas; nutritional supplements and self-help literature (guides on beauty treatments, nutrition and fitness). Westerners began to perceive Ayurveda and Yoga as a mind-body medicine and as a preventive medicine that offers a positive lifestyle index. Ayurveda twinned with yoga (Ayuryoga) became a branded commodity in North American spa culture.

These new trends were prominent particularly in the United States and in Northern Europe. Images of the exotic East played a crucial role in certain sectors of the marketing of Ayurvedic products or treatments. Gradually, Ayurveda attained shape of health tourism that caters both to foreign tourists as well as urban and middle-class Indians.

Ayurvedic Pharmaceuticalisation and the Origins of Health Tourism

The discussions in the preceding sections make it possible to arrive at an inference that Ayurveda achieved more popularity in the context of globalisation due to its achievement of certain scientific fidelity and its capacity for cultural accommodation. On the other hand the capacity of Ayurveda to be able to pose as a fully-fledged alternate medical system had eroded. The result that arose is the pharmaceuticalisation of Ayurveda. Even while Ayurveda continues to attain more presence in the public mind through advertising and other methods, the entire system gradually reduced to a mere supplier of pharmaceutical products(Bode 2004).This new form of Ayurveda of which an integral part is health tourism is sought by westerners and the upper-middle class Indians in increasing numbers. Health spas, rejuvenating centres, packages for relaxation therapies, health promotion services such as oil massages, aromatherapy, lifestyle diet and nutritional counselling, spiritual healing, biofeedback, yoga, self-help books and websites and Ayurvedic medicines available in pharmacies features the prospects of health tourism in Ayurveda (Cohen 1998). Ayurvedic self-help literature is a domain in which women could participate and discuss women's health. In fact, one most significant change to Ayurveda

in the twentieth century is the active participation of women in medicine as authors and as physicians.

In 1970s and 80s, Asian medicines such as Traditional Chinese Medicine and Ayurveda became part of western medical pluralism as Complementary and Alternative Medicine (CAM). A fundamental question to be addressed is to find reasons for westerners' increasing interest in Eastern medical practices.

A historical reason for this new interest is the inherent defect of western medicine which is subject to philosophical reasoning that arose in the continent in seventeenth and eighteenth centuries. Accordingly mind and body were perceived as separate entities and only the latter was seen as a symptom-bearing organism. The western counterculture that became a wave in 1960s and 70s attacked materialistic values, scientific progress and exclusivist belief in technocratic solutions to problems of mankind. This created in many of them a desire to explore alternative lifestyles. The European new generation was set to experiment whatever comes in their way: fashions and drugs on one hand and Asian philosophies spanning from meditation to mysticism on the other (Roszak1970).

The response in Europe towards Asian medicines was however not uniform. The western orthodoxy of Catholic Church as well as the countries such as France was suspicious about the philosophical contradictions inherent in Asian medications (Fulder 1996). Cardinal Joseph Ratzinger (later, Pope Benedict XVI) held that westerners' reliance on Eastern techniques of meditation may erode Christian roots of European culture.

On the other hand there were two positive high-level government reports on Complementary and Alternative Medicine in the West: The Report of the House of Lords Select Committee on Science and Technology (Britain, 2000) and the Report of the White House Commission (USA, 2002). Both reports arrived at similar conclusions and recommended that their health systems should ensure access to complementary and alternative medicine wherever there is evidence of efficacy and appropriate regulatory mechanisms that enhance public safety. Consequently a more plural medical system was to develop in Western

Europe and North America. Thus the practices originating in Asia helped shape in the West a new medical counterculture.

One of the most salient features of Ayurveda in the West is that it does not form part of the medical mainstream. On the contrary, what the western clientele and the upper middle class consumers in India expect of Ayurvedic health tourism is to develop a lifestyle in order to strengthen immune system and to help prevent disease. They identify traditional Indian medicine as a kind of preventative mind-body medicine.

Westerners' perceptions about Ayurvedic health tourism in the previous decades is based on the popular writing in print and on the internet. Some scientific research texts have also made impact on them. Perhaps the first non-academic book to introduce Ayurveda to the West was Vasant Lad's *Ayurveda: The Science of Self-Healing* (1984). It gained such popularity so as to be translated into more than a dozen languages and distributed in at least twenty countries. Robert Svoboda's *Prakriti: Your Ayurvedic Constitution* (1988) also emerged as a popular text and it too was translated into more than a dozen languages. These books and the Ayurvedic narratives that spread over internet capitalize on the romance of both India and alternative therapies. Thus it is to be inferred that in the West, Ayurveda functions on a public culture beyond academia.

One last question to be addressed in this paper is about the necessity to maintain standardization in Ayurvedic products in order to flourish health tourism. The internal structure and epistemology of this knowledge system depends heavily on its capability to standardize itself. Ayurvedic medicines are combination drugs composed of herbs, minerals and metals. From the perspective of modern manufacturing, the formulae and procedures laid down in classical Ayurvedic texts seems difficult and time consuming and hence the need for possible substitutes. The most important question is about what kind of mechanization would make it both economically viable and least harmful in terms of the sanctity of the processes? Pharmaceutical products in Ayurvedic tradition are now dominated by a few Indian companies such as Zandu, Dabur, Himalaya, AryaVaidya and Hamdard(Bode 2008).Along with pharmaceuticals, another contemporary trend is that the Ayurvedic health tourism industry

strives to expand their market. Popular media is extensively used for marketing. Research activities at various government and semi-governmental institutions such as AYUSH, CSIR and ICMR may also facilitate further development of Ayurvedic industry in general and health tourism in particular in Kerala in the next twenty five years.

Conclusion

Modernization of Ayurveda in Kerala and elsewhere in the context of colonial period of globalization resulted in its commercialization and in acculturation. Health tourism is the outcome of such complex interactions. India's medicine has always been subject to wide internal variations and different historical influences and cultural practices. Ayurvedic health tourism is the most contemporary of such trajectories shifts.

India is acquainted with a far larger number of medicinal plants than any other country on the face of the earth. If this and other such inherent advantages are re-oriented for the cultivation of faculties of Ayurvedic tourism, then it would serve not only as an economically sound industry but also to help solve analytical problems requiring deep introspection (Bose 1938).

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